

ISic0104

I.Sicily inscription 0104

Language

Latin

Type

building; honorific

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Excavated in piazza del Duomo

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico
Baldassare Romano, inventory 420

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---] Cn(aei) · f(ilius) · II · vir · quinq(uennalis) · [---]

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation (en)

...son of Gnaeus, quinquennial duumvir...

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285236

EDR 110876

EDCS 22100057

Bibliography

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Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7356 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650797>)

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 22

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